

Combating prostate cancer by sulfonamide compounds : Theoretical prediction

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Abstract : Prostate cancer is the second leading cause of cancer death and the mostly diagnosed form of cancer in men. The androgen receptor (AR) plays a crucial role in the development of the prostate as well as in prostate diseases. N-Butylbenzene-sulfonamide (NBBS) isolated from *P. africanum* and *Pseudomonas* sp. is responsible for AR inhibition and hence useful drug for the treatment of prostate cancer (PCa) and benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH). In the present study more than six hundred sulfonamides have been screened by molecular docking programme to search best suitable molecule for the treatment of PCa. Some sulfonamides have shown better docking score than approved PCa drug. DFT computation of optimized geometry of the sulfonamides and derivation of molecular orbitals has been used to correlate the drug likeness. Pharmacophore generation has been done to recognize the binding modes of inhibitors in the receptor active site. N-(3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dienyl)benzenesulfonamide, a phytochemical and 5-[3-(3-chloro-4-cyanophenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-4-oxo-2-sulfanylideneimidazolidin-1-yl]pyridine-3-sulfonamide, a synthetic molecule have shown best theoretical efficiency against AR.

Keywords : Sulfonamides, AR inhibitors and prostate cancer, structure based drug design, molecular docking, ADMET and DFT, pharmacophore generation.

Introduction

Prostate cancer (PCa) is the second most diagnosed cancer and is most common cancer in male in more than eighty countries¹. As a non-malignant form of prostate diseases benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is also a very common disease affecting aging of male with sometimes severe influence for quality of life². Both prostatic diseases, BPH and PCa, are characterized by the progressive enlargement of the prostate³⁻⁵. The androgen receptor (AR) plays an important role in the development of the prostate and in the development and progression of prostatic diseases. The AR is a nuclear hormone receptor that can be activated by androgens like testosterone and dihydrotestosterone (DHT)⁶. After androgen binding a conformational change of the AR is induced, followed by the translocation into the nucleus and the binding to androgen response elements of AR target

genes⁷. Hence, the AR acts as a transcription factor to transactivate or to inhibit gene expression, the transcriptional properties of the AR are partly dependent on binding of co-regulators (co-activators and co-repressors)⁸. As the AR is the main factor of PCa cell proliferation and progression the inhibition of the AR plays an important goal in PCa therapy⁹.

Since the late 1960s bark extracts of *Pygeum africanum* are used in Europe to treat BPH and several studies have confirmed the positive effect on prostatic diseases and also used to treat chest pain, malaria and fevers¹⁰. Recently, the ethanol extract of *P. africanum* has shown to inhibit human PCa cell growth, induces apoptosis and alter cell kinetics¹¹.

Two novel compounds from *P. africanum* : atraric acid (AA) and N-butylbenzene-sulfonamide (NBBS) were extracted and elicited the highest bioactivity as anti-androgenic compounds¹². NBBS is also produced

by some bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas*, and is found to exhibit a fungicidal activity¹³. NBBS is widely used as a plasticizer in polyacetals, polyamides, and polycarbonates and has been found in ground water and effluent from waste water treatment sites^{14,15}. The compound is lipophilic and distributes rapidly to the brain but also clears rapidly and shows little evidence of accumulation. Although NBBS is considered nonhazardous, some reports observed neuropathological injury over an extended period of exposure (by rats)¹⁵.

CH-5137291 is a synthetic small sulfonamide anti-androgen compound¹⁶. Pharmacological assay of CH-5137291 has been a potent AR pure antagonist which does not produce the agonist metabolite¹⁶. It inhibits completely AR-mediated transactivation and proliferation of the CRPC xenograft model LNCaP-BC2, which is bicalutamide (approved PCa drug) resistant¹⁷.

In this work, NBBS derivatives (total 638 molecules) and CH-5137291 (total 28 molecules) structure analogous are retrieved from the PubChem database¹⁸. They have been docked to examine their action against AR. Some structure analogous show higher docking score (binding affinity) than bicalutamide (approved PCa drug)^{19–21}. Drug likeness has been examined following Lipinski's rule of five²². The molecular orbitals are used to calculate the electronic configuration, molecular reactivity and stability of the compounds by Density functional theory (DFT)²³. Pharmacophore map generation has also been carried out to observe steric and electronic features of best docked structure analogues that ensured the optimal interactions with a receptor (AR) and to block its biological response²⁴. ADMET (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity) filtration has been applied to check toxicity of the compounds²⁵. N-(3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dienyl)benzenesulfonamide, a phytochemical and 5-[3-(3-chloro-4-cyanophenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-4-oxo-2-sulfanylideneimidazolidin-1-yl]pyridine-3-sulfonamide, a synthetic molecule, have shown best theoretical efficiency against AR.

Fig. 1. Function of Anti-AR drugs (AR : Androgen receptor; DHT : dihydrotestosterone).

Experimental

High throughput virtual screening (HTVS) :

Structure-based drug discovery is a vital process for fast and cost-effective lead discovery and proven to be more efficient than the conventional wet lab drug discovery²⁶. High-Throughput Screening (HTS) is an approach to drug discovery that has become a standard tool for structure-based drug discovery. It is basically a process of screening of large number of drug like molecules against selected and specific drug targets. HTS are used for screening of lead drug molecule including combinatorial chemistry, genomics, protein, and peptide libraries²⁷. The steps used in HTS are described below.

Drug-like amide molecule preparation :

A total of 638 derivatives of NBBS and 28 structures analogous of CH-5137291 have been collected from the PubChem database which shows inhibition of AR enzyme. Reference compounds of FDA (Food and Drug Administration) approved drug bicalutamide obtained from PubChem database¹⁸.

Docking preparation of AR :

In the present study AR of *Homo sapiens* has been retrieved from RCSB PDB database and the monomeric unit (A chain) has been used in the docking studies. GOLD (Genetic Optimization for Ligand Docking) software has been used for docking on Windows platform²⁸. It is a genetic algorithm for docking flexible ligands into protein binding sites. It has been tested on a large number of complexes extracted from the Protein Data Bank. The overall conclusion of these tests showed that the top-ranked GOLD solution has been correct in 70–82% of case²⁸.

Computation of drug-DNA interaction :

Drugs can interact with different coordinates (groove) of DNA, creating different binding patterns²⁹.

Each pattern has its own significance. Study and recognition of these patterns lead to fruitful estimate of binding modes and site selectivity which will be contributory for developments in the understanding of new drug molecules as potent and selective gene-regulatory drugs. To find the binding pattern of structural analogous with *Homo sapiens* DNA, docking method is used. Drug-DNA docking is done by AutoDock vina software³⁰.

ADMET and drug likeness :

Lipinski's rule of five (RO5) is used to filter orally active compounds as drugs and describes four simple physicochemical factors ranges (Mwt. < 500, log P < 5, H-bond donors < 5, H bond acceptors < 10) related with 90% of orally active drugs that have accomplished phase II clinical status²². These physicochemical factors are related with acceptable aqueous solubility and intestinal permeability and include the first steps in oral bioavailability. The RO5 has been purposely created to be a conservative predictor in a time period where medicinal and combinatorial chemistry created many compounds with very poor physicochemical properties. If a compound fails the RO5 there is a high chance that oral activity problems will be encountered by the drug like molecule. Because all parameters can be easily computed, the RO5 (or its variants) has become the most widely useful filter in virtual library design today.

Quantum chemistry calculation :

DFT (Density functional theory) has been done by Gaussian 09W on windows platform using Becke's three-parameter exchange potential and Lee-Yang-Parr correlation functional (B3LYP) theory with basis set 6-31G³²⁻³⁴. Afterward, surfaces (molecular orbital, density, potential) and electrostatics potential charges (EPS) were observed to calculate the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). HOMO and LUMO (the frontier molecular orbitals) are the most significant orbitals in a molecule³⁵. Interaction pattern of the molecule is dependent on these orbitals with other

molecules^{36,37}. Chemical reactivity, intermolecular interactions and kinetic stability of a molecule are characterized by the energy difference of HOMO-LUMO functions³⁸. Interaction between the HOMO of the drug (structural analogous) and the LUMO of the receptor (AR) is the key factor of drug activity. Tight binding of drugs with the receptor can be achieved by increasing HOMO energy and decreasing LUMO energy in the drug molecule³⁹.

Pharmacophore generation :

A pharmacophore model is an ensemble of steric and electronic features that is necessary to ensure the optimal supramolecular interactions with a specific biological target and to trigger (or block) its biological response⁴⁰. The generated pharmacophore models based on receptor-ligand interactions have confirmed all substantial interactions in the compound-receptor interaction modes⁴¹. In a structure-based pharmacophore model, possible interaction area between the drug target (receptor) and ligands are examined⁴². The structure-based pharmacophore (SBP) method employed in Discovery Studio is a typical example of a macromolecule-based approach. SBP converts LUDI interaction maps within the protein-binding site into catalyst pharmacophoric features : H-bond acceptor, H-bond donor and hydrophobe. The computer program LUDI is a new method for the *de novo* design of enzyme inhibitors⁴². Its interaction maps comprise of a large number of catalyst features⁴¹.

ADMET :

Before a drug to apply pharmacodynamics effect on the body via interaction with its target, it must transport through the body to reach the site of drug action. Pharmacokinetics denotes to the expedition of the drug from its point of entrance to the site of action. Generally speaking, this process can be defined by the following phases : absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity called ADMET⁴³. Competence of the drug to reach pharmacologically active concentration at the drug targets without any

undesirable effect is taken care by ADMET properties which include the calculation of a series of factors⁴⁴. ADMET has been done by evaluating water solubility, human intestinal absorption, oral bioavailability, blood-brain barrier penetration, transporter, plasma protein binding, volume of distribution, CYP450, toxicity etc. by support vector machine (SVM) algorithm⁴³.

Results and discussion

Docking and bond analysis :

The specific binding of a ligand (drug) to a target protein molecule is the key to drug action. Derivatives of NBBS (680 molecules), CH-5137291 (28 molecules) and bicalutamide (Scheme 1) used as drug source to find best docking pose in the protein structure. Each ligand binds favorably to a specific site on the surface of the target molecule. Identification of the ligand-binding site for each specific protein mol-

A:ASN705:HD22 – c5:F3, 2.06145 Å; A:THR877:HA – c5:F5, 2.15407 Å; A:ASN705:OD1 – c5:F4, 2.17797 Å; A:ASN705:HA – c5:O6, 2.86636 Å; A:THR877:O – c5:F5, 2.88652 Å; c5:H43 – A:MET745:O, 2.94028 Å; A:GLN711:HE21 – c5:N12, 2.18354 Å; c5:H45 – A:GLN711:OE1, 2.25387 Å; A:PHE764:HA – c5:O7, 2.40102 Å; c5:N13 – c5:F5, 3.10147 Å; c5:C16 – A:LEU704, 3.75721 Å and c5:C16 – A:LEU704, 3.75721 Å. The interaction of bicalutamide with the active site of *Homo sapience* AR shows interesting hydrogen bonds (Fig. 4) and some of the recognizable hydrogen bonds are A:VAL746:HA – BIC:F4, 2.36471 Å; BIC:O9 – BIC, 2.70794 Å; BIC:H35 – A:LEU704:O, 2.73955 Å; BIC:H39 – BIC, 2.88888 Å; A:MET745:C – BIC:F4, 2.97446 Å; BIC:N11 – BIC:F5, 3.01446 Å; BIC:H36 – A:LEU701:O, 3.05358 Å; A:MET745:O – BIC:F5, 3.46847 Å, BIC – A:LEU873, 3.63342 Å.

Scheme 1. Structures of NBBS, bicalutamide and CH-5137291.

ecule is crucially important when trying to find a suitable drug molecule for the target, but it is also important to understand the function of the protein⁴⁵.

NBBS structural analogue has been docked in the active site of *Homo sapience* AR. The hydrogen bond forming amino acids are ARG752 and PHE764. It forms three hydrogen bonds of A:ARG752:HH21 – NBBS:O2, 2.58227 Å; A:ARG752:HH22 – NBBS:O2, 2.42203 Å; A:PHE764:HA – NBBS:O2, 2.61477 Å and noncovalent π --- π interaction observe at 3.99411 Å (Fig. 2). The GOLD score is 62.72. Similarly CH-5137291 structural analogue interacts with protein and recognizable hydrogen bonds (Fig. 3) are

Fig. 2. NBBS structural analogue and *Homo sapience* AR after docking. Structure of N-butylbenzene-sulfonamide is added inset.

Fig. 3. CH-5137291 structural analogue and *Homo sapiens* AR after docking. Structure of CH-5137291 is added inset.

Fig. 4. Bicalutamide and *Homo sapiens* AR after docking. Structure of bicalutamide is added inset.

Drug-DNA interaction :

The Drug (NBBS and CH-5137291 structure analogous)-DNA interactions have been computationally examined by docking techniques³⁰. Binding pattern of drug with DNA shows that the drug interacts AT-rich regions of DNA in the minor groove by forming hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions (Fig. 5). Noncovalent bonds between NBBS structure analogous and DNA are mainly hydrogen bonds and

Fig. 5. NBBS structure analogous interaction to DNA in minor groove. Interactions of ligand with DNA base pairs (A, T, G, C).

the recognized bonds NBBS:H – L:DT38:O2, 2.42446 Å; L:DG39:H5'2 – :NBBS:O, 2.78442 Å; NBBS:H – L:DT38:O2, 2.94713 Å. Similar noncovalent interaction between CH-5137291 structure analogous and DNA are also mainly hydrogen bonds (Fig. 6); these are – c5:H43 – K:DG16:O3', 3.01246 Å; L:DG39:C5' – c5:O18, 3.42443 Å; c5:N25 – c5:F33, 3.44095 Å; c5:N25 – c5:F31, 3.44336 Å; L:DC42:C5' – c5:N25, 3.49813 Å and L:DG40:C4' – c5:O8, 3.54585 Å.

Density functional theory (DFT) analysis :

DFT optimized structures of NBBS and CH-5137291 have been used to determine the HOMO

Fig. 6. CH-5137291 structure analogous interaction to DNA in minor groove.

and LUMO energy, and the difference in HOMO-LUMO is the band gap. It indicates the suitability of electronic excitation that is necessary to compute the molecular reactivity and stability of the compounds. For NBBS and CH-5137291 structure analogous the band gap is smaller than bicalutamide (Fig. 7, Table 1).

Pharmacophore generation :

The generated pharmacophore models based on receptor-ligand interactions by docking have confirmed all major interactions in the drug-receptor interaction modes. The number of features, feature set, and selectivity score from pharmacophore generation were observed from the two best docked molecules.

Fig. 7. HOMO and LUMO of NBBS (a, b), CH-5137291 (c, d) and bicalutamide (e, f).

Table 1. The HOMO and LUMO of NBBS, CH-5137291 and bicalutamide

	HOMO	LUMO	BAND gap
Bicalutamide	-0.227079	-0.031292	-0.195787
CH-5137291	-0.252341	-0.104128	-0.148213
NBBS SA	-0.256383	-0.076092	-0.180291

Pharmacophore generation of NBBS, CH-5137291 structure analogous and bicalutamide are shown in Fig. 8.

ADMET property analysis :

There are total 26 parameters in ADMET data extracted from the PubMed and Google Scholar searches from 2002 to 2011⁴⁴. Pharmacokinetic properties and toxicities were predicted by ADMET which can predict permeability for BBB (blood-brain barrier), HIA (human intestinal absorption), P-glycopro-

Fig. 8. Pharmacophore features of NBBS (a); CH-5137291 (b); and bicalutamide (c) based on Receptor-Ligand Pharmacophore Generation.

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tein Substrate/Inhibitor, renal organic cation transporter, etc. ADMET result shows that the structure analogous are positive (+) in HIA, BBB permeability which suggest that the molecule is well absorbed in human body (Table 2)⁴⁵. Inhibition and initiation of P-glycoprotein have been reported as the causes of drug-drug interactions⁴⁶. Two best docked molecules are P-glycoprotein non-inhibitor which implies that

Table 2. ADMET properties of NBBS and CH-5137291 structure analogous (SA)

Model NBBS SA	Result	Probability	Model CH-5137291 SA	Result	Probability
Absorption					
Blood-Brain Barrier	BBB+	0.9582	Blood-Brain Barrier	BBB+	0.5940
Human Intestinal Absorption	HIA+	1.0000	Human Intestinal Absorption	HIA+	0.9954
Caco-2 Permeability	Caco2-	0.6072	Caco-2 Permeability	Caco2-	0.5626
P-Glycoprotein Substrate	Non-substrate	0.6861	P-Glycoprotein Substrate	Non-substrate	0.8439
P-Glycoprotein Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.7413	P-Glycoprotein Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.7052
	Inhibitor	0.6465		Non-inhibitor	0.7123
Renal Organic Cation Transporter	Non-inhibitor	0.7756	Renal Organic Cation Transporter	Non-inhibitor	0.8974
Distribution					
Subcellular localization	Lysosome	0.5388	Subcellular localization	Mitochondria	0.5079
Metabolism					
CYP450 2C9 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.7111	CYP450 2C9 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.6431
CYP450 2D6 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.8138	CYP450 2D6 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.7821
CYP450 3A4 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.5633	CYP450 3A4 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.5548
CYP450 1A2 Inhibitor	Inhibitor	0.5541	CYP450 1A2 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.7698
CYP450 2C9 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.6275	CYP450 2C9 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.6453
CYP450 2D6 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.7480	CYP450 2D6 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.8638
CYP450 2C19 Inhibitor	Inhibitor	0.6805	CYP450 2C19 Inhibitor	Inhibitor	0.6259
CYP450 3A4 Inhibitor	Inhibitor	0.5000	CYP450 3A4 Inhibitor	Inhibitor	0.5556
CYP Inhibitory Promiscuity	High CYP Inhibitory Promiscuity	0.6834	CYP Inhibitory Promiscuity	Low CYP Inhibitory Promiscuity	0.5698
Toxicity					
Human Ether-à-go-go-Related Gene Inhibition	Weak inhibitor	0.5237	Human Ether-à-go-go-Related Gene Inhibition	Weak inhibitor	0.9963
	Non-inhibitor	0.8334		Non-inhibitor	0.7439
AMFS Toxicity	Non AMES toxic	0.7346	AMES Toxicity	Non AMES toxic	0.7020
Carcinogens	Non-carcinogens	0.7546	Carcinogens	Non-carcinogens	0.6779
Fish Toxicity	High FHMT	0.9839	Fish Toxicity	High FHMT	0.9608
Tetrahymena Pyriformis Toxicity	High TDT	0.9918	Tetrahymena Pyriformis Toxicity	High TPT	0.7193
Honey Bee Toxicity	High HBT	0.6460	Honey Bee Toxicity	Low HBT	0.8912
Biodegradation	Not ready	0.8827	Biodegradation	Not ready	1.0000
Acute Oral Toxicity	III	0.6253	Acute Oral Toxicity	III	0.6420
Carcinogenicity (Three-class)	Non-required	0.5896	Carcinogenicity (Three-class)	Non-required	0.6386

the two best docked molecules won't interact with other drugs. Organic cation transporters are responsible for drug absorption and disposition in the kidney, liver and intestine⁴⁷. ADMET data of two docked molecules show that they will be non-inhibitor of renal organic cation transporter. The human cytochromes P450 (CYPs), particularly isoforms 1A2, 2C9, 2D6 and 3A4, are responsible for about 90% oxidative metabolic reactions. Inhibition of CYP enzymes will lead to inductive or inhibitory failure of drug metabolism⁴⁸.

The Ames test is a widely employed method that uses bacteria to test whether a given chemical can cause cancer. More formally, it is a biological assay to evaluate the mutagenic potential of chemical compounds^{49,50}. ADMET result shows two best docked molecules were non-Ames toxic and non-carcinogenic.

Human Ether-à-go-go-Related Gene (hERG) is a gene sensitive to drug binding⁵¹. ADMET result shows two best docked molecules were weak inhibitor and non-inhibitor of hERG inhibition (predictor I and II). That means two best docked molecules will bind well with Receptor⁵². Understanding of ADMET properties, together with their measurement and prediction gives idea about properties that provide information about dose size and dose frequency, drugs solubility, metabolism of drug and its toxicity. Before synthesizing drug like molecules in laboratory knowledge of drug properties will help to save time and resources.

Conclusion

Both the natural (NBBS) and synthetic (CH-5137291) sulfonamide derivatives show potent anti-prostate cancer activity. The best docked compounds have better docking score than approved cancer drugs, and also show better ADMET efficiency. Molecular orbital, pharmacophore, drug likeness, ADMET gave idea about electrostatic pharmacological and nontoxic properties. The computational prediction may be useful for experimental pharmaceutical or medicinal chemists to synthesize analogous molecule and may examine against prostate cancer cells.

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